

**EFFECTIVENESS OF VIDEO ASSISTED TEACHING PROGRAM
(VATP) ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING DISASTER
MANAGEMENT AMONG ACCREDITED SOCIAL HEALTH
ACTIVIST (ASHA) WORKERS AT PRIMARY
HEALTH CENTRES IN PUDUCHERRY**

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Disaster is a sudden ecologic phenomenon of sufficient magnitude to require external assistance. Disaster impacts are extreme occurrences that disrupt daily life, destroy infrastructure (including homes, hospitals, and other buildings, as well as roads, bridges, power lines, and other structures), disrupt electricity, cause fatalities, and have other severe repercussions. **Methodology:** Quantitative research approach and Pre experimental - one group pre test and post test research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in selected Primary Health Centres in Puducherry. The total sample size of this study was 192 ASHA workers who was selected using Purposive sampling technique. **Results:** Out of 192 ASHA workers, in pre test level of knowledge, 153 (79.7 %) ASHA's had inadequate knowledge and 39 (20.3%) ASHA's had moderately adequate knowledge. Whereas in post test level of knowledge, 176 (91.7%) ASHA's had adequate knowledge and 16 (8.3%) ASHA's had moderately adequate knowledge. **Conclusion:** This study revealed that Video Assisted Teaching Program was effective in improving the level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers.

Keyword: Disaster management, Knowledge, Video assisted teaching, ASHA Workers.

INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization (WHO) defines —Disaster is a sudden ecologic phenomenon of sufficient magnitude to require external assistance.⁴ Natural and man-made disasters are the two basic categories of disasters. Natural disasters are caused by natural occurrences such as hurricanes, cyclones, earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, tidal waves, landslides, volcanic eruptions, tornadoes, fires, heat waves, famines, and epidemics. Human activity causes man-made disasters, such as industrial accidents, armed conflicts, terrorism, political unrest, building collapses, toxicological accidents, nuclear mishaps, and war¹.

Disaster impacts are extreme occurrences that disrupt daily life, destroy infrastructure (including homes, hospitals, and other buildings, as well as roads, bridges, power lines, and other structures), disrupt electricity, cause fatalities, and have other severe repercussions.^{2,3}

The physical impacts of disasters include casualties and property damage like burns, epidemics, physical illnesses, sanitation problems, reproductive health issues, and miscarriages, the disaster also had economic and social effects like changes in people's roles in society, and social disruptions.⁴ Emergency preparedness right at the grass-root level is essential to manage disasters effectively. Local infrastructure and a well-trained human resource available immediately following disasters are key stakeholders in disaster management. The frontline health workers have the main role in disaster management as they are the first contact of the community to the health system, especially in rural areas⁵.

The public health system must prioritize disaster preparedness and effective administration due to the increasing frequency and severity of natural catastrophes. All tiers of the health system should cultivate a culture of resilience. At the local level, emergency planning is crucial for efficient disaster management. The availability of well-trained ASHA workers and strengthening local infrastructure following disasters are crucial elements in disaster management.⁶

NEED FOR THE STUDY

According to the Emergency Event Database EM-DAT, there were 387 natural disasters and hazards globally in 2022 that claimed 30,704 lives and had an impact on 185 million people. The amount of economic losses was about 223.8 billion. In Europe, heat waves contributed to

nearly 16,000 more deaths, whilst 88.9 million people in Africa were afflicted by droughts. The impact of disasters on people and the economy was disproportionately greater in Africa, as seen by the 16.4% share of fatalities compared to 3.8% in the previous two decades. Despite having some of the most devastating disasters in 2022, it was relatively lower in Asia.

Globally, the number of people killed by natural catastrophes decreased significantly throughout the course of the 20th century. The yearly average in the early 1900s was frequently between 4,00,000 and 5,00,000 deaths. We have observed a notable fall to less than 1,00,000 in the second part of the century and into the early 2000s.– at least five times lower than these peaks.⁷

According to the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, 321 instances of natural disasters affected 108 core people in India from 2000 to 2019 and claimed the lives of 79,732 individuals.⁸

Tamil Nadu (TN), is prone to a variety of dangers. There are 14 coastal districts out of 38 districts along the 1,076 km long coastline. People who live in coastal districts face a constant hazard as a result of the more than 50 cyclones that have ravaged the TN coast during the previous century at various sites. Other common disasters in the state, besides cyclones, include floods, landslides, droughts, sea erosion, heat waves, thunderstorms, and lightning, as well as fire accidents, forest fires, and industrial & chemical disasters.⁹

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study to evaluate the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Program (VATP) on knowledge regarding Disaster Management among Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA) Workers at Primary Health Centers in Puducherry.

Objectives of the study:

- To assess the existing level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA Workers.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Program on knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA Workers.

- To associate the post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA Workers with selected demographic variables.

DELIMITATION:

The study is delimited to 192 ASHA workers, Primary Health Centers, Puducherry and Period of 4 weeks.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Quantitative research approach and Pre experimental - one group pre test and post test research design was adopted for the study. • Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC) of MTPG & RIHS, Puducherry for conducting the study. The study was conducted in selected Primary Health Centres in Puducherry. The total sample size of this study was 192 ASHA workers who was selected using Purposive sampling technique. Inclusion criteria includes who are willing to participate in the study and Able to understand Tamil and English. Exclusion criteria includes the ASHA Workers those who were, sick on the day of data collection and attended disaster management training program during the last 6 months.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Prior the data collection, formal permission was obtained from the college authorities. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of MTPG&RIHS, Puducherry. Formal permission was obtained from the Director of Health and Family Welfare Services, and Deputy Directorate of Public Health, Government of Puducherry and concerned medical officer in PHC's, Puducherry. The period of data collection was one month.

The researcher selected 192 ASHA's by adopting purposive sampling technique. Each day 2 to 3 PHC's were covered. All ASHA's working in concerned PHC was gathered in a common place. The researcher introduced herself to the ASHA workers and explained the purpose of the study and also assured that the data obtained will be kept confidential. The ASHA's had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. Written consent was obtained

from the individual ASHA workers. Demographic variables were collected and structured questionnaire was distributed to ASHA workers, to assess the existing level of knowledge regarding disaster management and 30 minutes was given for them to answer the questions. On the same day, after completion of pretest, ASHA workers were educated regarding disaster management through power point presentation consisting of 33 slides and disaster management video play for a total duration of 30 minutes. Around 15 - 20 ASHA's were assessed per day approximately, depending on the distance between the PHC's and the researchers institution. On the 8th day, post test was assessed by using the same tool. All the ASHA's had cooperated well throughout the data collection period. The data collection schedule is enclosed in the Annexure XI.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of demographic variables revealed that in terms of age, the majority of ASHA workers, 89 (46.4%), fell within the age group of 36 - 45 years. Following this, 78 (40.6%) were in the 31 – 35 age bracket, 23 (12.0%) were aged 26 – 30, and only 2 (1.0%) were between 21 – 25 years old. In regards to educational attainment, 87 (45.3%) had completed 10th grade, 69 (35.9%) had finished 12th grade, and 36 (18.8%) had obtained a bachelor's degree. Considering their area of residence, 99 (51.6%) resided in urban regions, while 93 (48.4%) lived in rural areas. Examining their sources of previous knowledge, the majority, 163 (84.9%), cited TV news, followed by 15 (7.8%) who relied on newspapers, and 14 (7.3%) who used the internet for information on disaster management. Related to the experienced any type of disaster, 192 (100%) had experience the flood, storm, tsunami, earthquake and COVID 19. Considering the working experience in disaster management, mostly 153 (79.7%) had work experience in COVID 19 disaster management activities collaborated with other health care personnel's and 39 (20.3%) not had worked in disaster management.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of pre and post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers. N = 192

LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST	
	Frequency No.	Percentage (%)	Frequency No.	Percentage (%)
Inadequate knowledge	153	79.7	0	0.0
Moderately Adequate Knowledge	39	20.3	16	8.3
Adequate knowledge	0	0.0	176	91.7

The above table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of pre and post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers. Out of 192 ASHA workers, in pre test level of knowledge, 153 (79.7 %) ASHA’s had inadequate knowledge and 39 (20.3%) ASHA’s had moderately adequate knowledge. Whereas in post test level of knowledge, 176 (91.7%) ASHA’s had adequate knowledge and 16 (8.3%) ASHA’s had moderately adequate knowledge.

Figure 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of pre and post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers

Table 2: Effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Program on knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers. N =

192

LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	PAIRED 't' TEST	'p' VALUE
Pre test	8.46	2.55	t = 53.124	p = 0.000 S***
Post test	25.64	3.60		

p<0.01, *p<0.001, S – Significant

The above table shows that showed the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Program on knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers. Out of 192 ASHA workers, in pre test, mean and standard deviation knowledge score was 8.46 ± 2.55 and in post test, mean and standard deviation knowledge score was 25.64 ± 3.60 . The findings reveals that calculated 't' value was 53.124 was found to be statistically significant at $p<0.001$. This study evident that Video Assisted Teaching Program on knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers had significant improvement in their post test level of knowledge and thus proving that Video Assisted Teaching Program was effective.

Figure:2 Effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Program on knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers.

On association, the data shows the association between the post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management with selected demographic variables among ASHA workers. There is a significant association between the post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers with area of residence ($p < 0.05$) and source of previous knowledge about disaster ($p < 0.01$).

Other demographic variables such as age group, educational status, experienced any type of disaster and working experience in disaster management program had not shown significant association with post test level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concluded that knowledge regarding disaster management is very important as it impacts their response during any emergency situation. This study revealed that Video Assisted Teaching Program was effective in improving the level of knowledge regarding disaster management among ASHA workers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Replication of the study may be done with the large samples in different settings to generalize the study findings.
- Similar study can be conducted with other health care professionals, volunteers, school and college teachers and self-help groups.
- Similar study can be done with control group among ASHA workers
- Similar study can be conducted with comparative group of other health care professionals.

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